

INTRODUCTION

- Autosomal Dominant Polycystic Kidney Disease (ADPKD) is a hereditary disorder marked by fluid-filled cysts formation [1] and peritubular interstitial fibrosis from non-cystic tissue, which contribute to renal function decline [2]
- While traditional monitoring focuses on total kidney and cyst volume, recent insights highlight the significance of evaluating non-cystic tissue [2]
- Multi-parametric MRI (mp-MRI), combining anatomical T1-weighted (T1-w) and T2-weighted (T2-w) and diffusion-weighted imaging (DWI), offers a non-invasive method to assess non-cystic tissue
- Recently, radiomics has been proposed for classification and prediction of ADPKD stage and progression, but suffers from robustness and stability issues

AIM

We propose a novel framework to identify reliable radiomic features for characterizing non-cystic tissue using multi-parametric MRI. Our approach focuses on evaluating radiomic reliability through reproducible and informative features, considering three segmentation methods (manual and automatic) as a key source of variability.

DATASET

The dataset includes 14 ADPKD patients from the EuroCYST initiative, specifically from Istituto di Ricerche Farmacologiche Mario Negri IRCCS, Bergamo, Italy. T1-w, T2-w, and DWI scans with multiple b-values (0, 15, 50, 100, 200, 350, 500, 700, and 1000 s/mm²) were acquired, with the DWI scans following the IntraVoxel Incoherent Motion (IVIM) model. All imaging was performed without contrast media, in accordance with the CRISP protocol [3].

METHODS

IVIM parametric maps (D, f, and D*) were obtained from DWI images using a fully connected deep neural network (DNN) [4].

Non-cystic tissue was identified using a manual Ground Truth (GT) and a Deep Learning Network for identifying cysts [5] on T2-weighted images. The non-cystic region was obtained by subtracting the cystic tissue from the total kidney volume (DL_{start}). A post-processed version (DL_{adj}) was created by removing vessels, fat, and hemorrhagic cysts with mp-MRI. The agreement with the manual GT was measured using the Dice index.

92 radiomics features were extracted from each image and segmentation, considering the two kidney separately. Radiomic feature reliability was assessed using Intraclass Correlation Coefficients (ICC) across different non-cystic segmentations. Features were reliable if:

- Reproducible: ICC>0.8 between regions of interest (ROIs) with similar information content (GT and DL_{adj});
- Informative: ICC<0.5 between ROIs with different content (GT and DL_{start}).

Subsequently, the percentage of reliable features for each image type was determined.

RESULTS

Segmentation results on T2-w showed the DL_{adj} segmentation closer to the GT compared to the DL_{start}. Dice scores revealed a stronger agreement between DL_{adj} and GT (Dice = 0.69 ± 0.08) compared to DL_{start} and GT (Dice = 0.51 ± 0.11).

Radiomic reliability is higher for DL_{adj} segmentation, notably for IVIM maps (ICC > 0.8). DL_{adj} exhibited lower reproducibility for T1-w and T2-w images, while DL_{start} demonstrated higher ICC values for these images.

		GT	DL _{start}	DL _{adj}
f	GT	1.00	0.28	0.86
	DL _{start}	0.28	1.00	0.28
	DL _{adj}	0.86	0.28	1.00
D	GT	1.00	0.26	0.81
	DL _{start}	0.26	1.00	0.30
	DL _{adj}	0.81	0.30	1.00
D*	GT	1.00	0.41	0.89
	DL _{start}	0.41	1.00	0.43
	DL _{adj}	0.89	0.43	1.00
T2-w	GT	1.00	0.61	0.49
	DL _{start}	0.61	1.00	0.69
	DL _{adj}	0.49	0.69	1.00
T1-w	GT	1.00	0.70	0.51
	DL _{start}	0.70	1.00	0.40
	DL _{adj}	0.51	0.40	1.00

The percentage of reliable features for each image, grouped by radiomic feature classes, shows FO and GLCM for D and f parametric maps as the most reliable features, with T1-w and T2-w images showing lower reliability.

FO: First Order; GLCM: Gray-Level Co-Occurrence Matrix; GLDM: Gray-Level Dependence Matrix; GLRLM: Gray-Level Run Length Matrix; GLSZM: Gray-Level Size Zone Matrix; NGTDM: Neighbouring Gray Tone Difference Matrix

CONCLUSIONS

Texture information from diffusion and flowing fraction IVIM maps effectively characterizes the non-cystic parenchymal region, providing both informative and resilient to minor segmentation discrepancies, mostly within the FO and GLCM feature classes. On the contrary, the low contrast among tissues in T1-w and T2-w images makes them unreliable for non-cystic characterization.

Our study highlights the robustness and reliability of radiomic features extracted from D and f IVIM maps in analyzing non-cystic kidney parenchyma in ADPKD patients, contrary to anatomical images that lack the required informativeness.

REFERENCES

- Caroli et al.: Intermediate volume on computed tomography imaging defines a fibrotic compartment that predicts glomerular filtration rate decline in autosomal dominant polycystic kidney disease patients. *The American Journal of Pathology* 179(2), 619–627 (2011)
- Caroli et al.: Abdominal imaging in adpkd: Beyond total kidney volume. *Journal of Clinical Medicine* 12(15), 5133 (2023)
- Chapman et al.: Renal structure in early autosomal-dominant polycystic kidney disease (adpkd): The consortium for radiologic imaging studies of polycystic kidney disease (crisp) cohort. *Kidney International* 64(3), 1035–1045 (2003)
- Mastropietro et al.: A supervised deep neural network approach with standardized targets for enhanced accuracy of ivim parameter estimation from multi-snr images. *NMR in Biomedicine* 35(10), e4774 (2022)
- Kline et al.: Automatic semantic segmentation of kidney cysts in mr images of patients affected by autosomal-dominant polycystic kidney disease. *Abdominal Radiology* 46, 1053–1061 (2021)

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